

MODELLING OF THE HiPerDiF METHOD FOR MANUFACTURING RECYCLED COMPOSITES USING SMOOTHED PARTICLE HYDRODYNAMICS

Samantha Huntley^{1*}, Thomas Rendall¹, Marco Longana¹, Thomas Pozegic¹, Juhyeong Lee¹, Kevin Potter¹ and Ian Hamerton¹

¹ Bristol Composites Institute (ACCIS), Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, Bristol, U.K.

* Corresponding author (samantha.huntley@bristol.ac.uk)

Keywords: Recycling, Aligned discontinuous fibres, Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics

ABSTRACT

There has been a significant increase in the amount of carbon fibre reinforced polymer composite production in recent years with this trend set to continue in the future. With this increase in production comes an increase in waste. The High Performance Discontinuous Fibre (HiPerDiF) method invented at the University of Bristol is a technology enabling remanufacturing of carbon fibres reclaimed from end-of-life and production waste into recycled composite materials. It does this through a mechanism that ensures a high level of fibre alignment, a key requirement in order to produce commercially valuable, discontinuous fibre composites. The fibre alignment is enabled by spraying the short fibres, suspended in a water jet, between thinly spaced, parallel plates. This work models this fluid dynamics alignment mechanism using smoothed particle hydrodynamics. The results shown here validate the model against experiments by showing that the computational model captures the overall effect of changing the plate spacing on the fibre alignment. This is important to give confidence in using the model to investigate the physics behind the alignment in more detail.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades there has been an increase in the production of composite materials. This has resulted in a need to find ways of dealing with the increasing amount of production waste and end-of-life products. One possible solution is to recycle the material, which for thermosetting-based composites, involves reclaiming the fibres by degrading the matrix and remanufacturing the fibres into a reusable material. During this process the fibres are cut into short lengths. A technology, invented at the University of Bristol, called the High Performance Discontinuous Fibre (HiPerDiF) method, enables the production of commercially valuable and high performance recycled composite materials by remanufacturing the reclaimed fibres into highly aligned discontinuous fibre composites [1]. There are also advantages to manufacturing composites using short fibres, which are not limited to recycled fibres, rather than continuous fibres. The advantages include increased ease of production of parts with complex geometries due to the better formability offered by short fibres; a reduction in manufacturing defects that can occur due to manipulations [2] and the ability to produce material which exhibits pseudo-ductile response under loading as a result of the fibres ability to deform and slip at the discontinuities [3]. The next stages for this technology involve upscaling the design from its current laboratory scale to a third generation, industrial-scale machine.

A high-level of alignment is crucial for the discontinuous fibre composites to achieve the same high specific strengths and moduli as the continuous fibre composites and thus take advantage of the benefits mentioned earlier. The high level of alignment is created by a momentum change caused by the short fibres, which are suspended in a water jet and sprayed through a nozzle, hitting a plate. This work aims to use smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) to investigate the fluid mechanics behind the HiPerDiF process. By accurately modelling the alignment mechanism of the current design any changes needed for the next generation machine can be simulated to determine the effect on the alignment before being

implemented. SPH has been chosen due to its excellent ability to model free-surface flows and cases with large amounts of deformation, such as will be the case in this application.

The alignment mechanism involves modelling short fibres suspended in fluid flow. In the literature, this has been done using SPH for reinforced concrete by Kulasegaram and Karihaloo [4] and Deeb *et al.* [5], both of which used an incompressible SPH method to model the rigid-body fibres in non-Newtonian flow. Other applications for this type of modelling are three-dimensional die-casting, which was considered by Cleary *et al.* [6-9], the injection moulding process [10-12] and three-dimensional printing [13]. All the applications just mentioned involve fluid that is much more viscous than present in this work. The suspension of fibres in a fluid creates a problem that has strongly coupled fluid-structure interactions and in order to model it the fibres are treated as rigid bodies. Modelling solids in this way within an SPH framework is a method that has been utilised by several authors in the literature. Tofighi *et al.* [14] used an incompressible two-dimensional SPH to study the flow around different shaped disks whilst Hashemi *et al.* [15] modelled the flow around circular solids using a two-dimensional weakly-compressible SPH method. Also, Aly and Asai [16] investigated the impact of flood disaster using incompressible SPH. All of these works were concerned with the simulation of only a single body rather than the multiple bodies that are present in this work.

As stated previously, the final alignment of the fibres influences the mechanical properties of the manufactured composite and, as such, it is important to have highly-aligned fibres in order to be able to manufacture structures that are competitive with traditional continuous fibre components. Fibre orientation using SPH for the injection molding process has been investigated by Skoptsov *et al.* [17] and for self-compacting concrete by Deeb *et al.* [18]. Other studies concerned with fibre orientation have not used SPH such as Khodadadi Yazdi *et al.* [19] and Oumer *et al.* [20]. The work of Hamalainen *et al.* [21] is particularly relevant for this application as it is concerned with the papermaking process, which is similar to the HiPerDiF method. The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: section 2 describes the HiPerDiF technology in greater detail; section 3 outlines the SPH methodology used in this work; section 4 presents the results whilst section 5 concludes the paper.

2 THE HIPERDIF TECHNOLOGY

The HiPerDiF method (Fig. 1) is used to manufacture composite tapes that are made up of discontinuous fibres (1 to 12mm in length). In the first stage, the short fibres are dispersed in a water suspension tank before being transferred through a series of pipes, *via* a peristaltic pump, to the fibre orientation or alignment head (Fig. 2); the latter consists of multiple nozzles and a series of parallel plates. In the alignment head, the nozzles are used to spray the fibres suspended in a water-jet between the parallel plates, the fibres then drop on to a perforated conveyer belt, which allows the water to be removed using a suction pump. This leaves the aligned fibres which can then be impregnated with the resin to form a composite tape.

From initial observations, it is the change in momentum, caused by the fibres hitting the plates, that causes the alignment. The HiPerDiF technology produces highly aligned composites with 67% of the fibres in the range of $\pm 3^\circ$ of perfect alignment for specimens with a volume fraction of 55% and this enables the production of materials with mechanical properties comparable to those of continuous fibres [22].

The work presented here is conducted as part of a wider project to upscale the HiPerDiF technology in order to achieve a higher production rate. The primary mechanism to achieve this is by an increased throughput of fibres. However, this must be accomplished without degrading the current high level of alignment of the fibres. The alignment mechanism is a fluid-structure interaction problem and this work aims to validate a computational model for this mechanism so that it can then be used to inform the next generation design.

Figure 1: HiPerDiF composite manufacturing process

Figure 2: HiPerDiF alignment head

3 METHODOLOGY

The HiPerDiF alignment mechanism is modelled using SPH (Fig. 3), a Lagrangian meshless particle method for solving the equations of fluid dynamics. The partial differential equations are converted into ordinary differential equations using information from discretized particles with material physical properties. Then, the ordinary differential equations can be integrated with respect to time alone. The weakly compressible form of the SPH equations are used. The momentum equation is given in Eq. (1); the right-hand side consists of a pressure term, a viscosity term proposed by Morris *et al.* [23], a pairwise force surface tension described by Tartakovsky and Meakin [24] and gravity. The continuity equation is given in Eq. (2) and the right-hand side is an approximation to $u \cdot \nabla \rho$ because $\nabla \cdot u = 0$, as this is incompressible. Wendland's C2 kernel is used throughout this work. Tait's equation of state is used to compute the pressures. The solid plate boundary conditions are modelled using dynamic boundary particles [25], and the equations are evolved using the Newmark-*beta* scheme as explained by Hall *et al.* [26].

$$\frac{Du_i}{Dt} = - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \left[\frac{p_j}{\rho_j^2} + \frac{p_i}{\rho_i^2} \right] \nabla W_{ij} + \sum_{j=1}^N m_j v \frac{\rho_i + \rho_j}{\rho_i \rho_j} \frac{x_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij}}{|x_{ij}|^2 + 0.001h^2} u_{ij} + \frac{1}{m_i} \sum_{j=1}^N f_{ij} + g \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j (u_i - u_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} \quad (2)$$

3.1 Surface tension model

The surface tension model of Tartakovsky and Meakin [24] is implemented as pair-wise forces between particles. The formulation of the force is motivated by its molecular origins such that is repulsive at short range, attractive at medium range and decays to zero at long range. The force term is given by Eq. (3), where the term s_{ij} determines the strength of the force and is dependent on the surface tension coefficient of the fluid and the contact angles of the solids (fibres and plates) as explained by Tartakovsky and Panchenko [27]. The values used in this work are given in section 4.

$$f_{ij} = \begin{cases} -s_{ij} \cos\left(\frac{3\pi}{4h}|x_{ij}|\right) \frac{x_{ij}}{|x_{ij}|} & |x_{ij}| < 2h \\ 0 & |x_{ij}| > 2h \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: SPH of the HiPerDiF alignment head

3.2 Fibre model

The fibres are also simulated using the SPH formulation but are treated as rigid bodies. Each fibre consists of a number of SPH particles, so that both momentum (Eq. (1)) and continuity (Eq. (2)) are solved for each fibre particle. The linear and angular velocities, U and Ω respectively, of each fibre can then be updated by summing the force contribution from the particles that belong to it and updating the values according to rigid body kinematics (Eqs. (4) and (5))

$$M \frac{dU}{dt} = F \quad (4)$$

$$I \frac{d\Omega}{dt} = T \quad (5)$$

where M is the mass of the fibre, F is the total force on the fibre computed by summing the contribution from the particles that belong to it, I is the inertia matrix, and T is the torque. The fibres are modelled as thin rods meaning that there is no rotation about length.

4 RESULTS

The aim of this paper is to validate the computational method used to simulate the alignment mechanism of the HiPerDiF process [28]. This has been achieved by qualitatively comparing the alignment of the fibre preform produced by a small first-generation HiPerDiF prototype machine against the simulation results.

4.1 Experimental setup

The small HiPerDiF prototype machine comprises two nozzles and was run using three different spacings of the parallel plates (0.3 mm, 0.5 mm, and 1.0 mm), while all other settings remained constant: the total flow rate was 2.35 mL/s, the belt speed was 14 mm/s, the nozzle diameter was 1.35 mm, and the nozzles were inclined 45 degrees to the horizontal and the vertical. The carbon fibres used were 3 mm in length with a specific density of 1.82.

4.2 Computational setup

The computational simulations were designed so that they matched the experiments as closely as possible. A large number of the parameters are directly set by the values used in the experiments, and as such simple to implement. This includes the nozzle angles, belt speed and fibre properties. The fluid jet velocity was modelled as a sinusoidal function as the HiPerDiF machine uses a peristaltic pump to spray the fluid/fibre mixture between the parallel plates. The magnitude of the function was chosen so that the overall flow rate matched the value recorded in the experiments and the frequency was set to 0.025 seconds on and 0.025 seconds off, also to match the experimental values. The initial particle spacing used in the simulations is a trade-off between accuracy and computational cost, but in this work, it is primarily driven by the requirement to adequately resolve the gap between the parallel plates. In order to achieve this an initial particle spacing of 0.06 mm was used in all the simulations. The fibre concentration within the water jet was modelled assuming that the fibres were evenly dispersed, which lead to four fibres per nozzle per pulse. All the simulation parameters are provided in Table 1.

Parameter name	Value	Units
Initial particle spacing	0.06	mm
Surface tension coefficient	0.0728	N/m
Smoothing length	0.09	mm
Contact angle (plates)	71.0	degrees
Contact angle (fibres)	60.0	degrees
Timestep size	2×10^{-7}	seconds
FSI loop iterations	2	n/a

Table 1: Computational parameters

4.3 Validation results

For each plate spacing, the machine was run, and the resulting preform transferred to a glass slide. An image was taken of each preform and these are shown in Fig. 4 (left), which clearly shows a decrease in alignment as the spacing between the plates is increased. The simulation results are shown on the right-hand side of Fig. 4. It can be seen that the simulations capture the overall effect of changing the plate spacing in that, as with the experiments, as the plate spacing is increased the alignment of the fibres decreases.

Figure 4: Fibre alignment from experiments (left) and simulations (right) for plate spacings of 0.3 mm (top), 0.5 mm (middle), and 1 mm (bottom)

The alignment can also be quantified and is done so easily using the computational model. In this work, the metric used for alignment quantification is the same as in the paper by Yu *et al.* [22], where the HiPerDiF technology was first presented. This metric is the percentage of fibres with an orientation of $\pm 3^\circ$. The fibre alignment of the computational results for the three plate spacings is shown in Fig. 5, which confirms the findings of the visual inspection of the fibre alignment. The smallest plate spacing has 76% of fibres aligned within $\pm 3^\circ$ which is almost three times more than the largest plate spacing, which gave 27% of fibres aligned within $\pm 3^\circ$. This gives an indication of the effect of the plate spacing on the quality of the composite tape as the alignment significantly affects the mechanical properties. All alignment values are listed in Table 2.

Figure 5: Effect of plate spacing on fibre alignment (% aligned within $\pm 3^\circ$)

4.4 Effect of multiple fibre lengths

Once the computational model has been validated it can then be used to investigate how the different parameters affect the alignment of the fibres. As the HiPerDiF technology is designed to use recycled carbon fibres and part of the recycling process is to chop the fibres into smaller lengths, this can result in fibres of different lengths being produced. Therefore, a simulation was setup to investigate the effect of using different length fibres. The fibres had lengths of 3 mm, 4.5 mm, and 6 mm. The case was modelled with the same concentration of the three fibre lengths, the plate spacing was 0.3 mm and all other parameters were the same as listed in Table 1. The resulting fibres are shown in Fig. 6. It can be

seen that the overall alignment of the fibres is similar to the results using the 3mm fibres only. The percentage of fibres within $\pm 3^\circ$ is 66%. By using the computational model, it is also possible to calculate the alignment of the different length fibres which was 46%, 67%, and 85% for the 3 mm, 4.5 mm, and 6 mm. This suggests that the presence of longer fibres slightly deteriorates the alignment of the shortest fibres but also indicates that the alignment is primarily caused by the fibres hitting the plates and therefore longer fibres are more restricted in the orientation for a given plate spacing resulting in a higher level of alignment for longer fibres. Caution must be applied before extrapolating this result to much longer fibres as it is assumed in this work that the fibres are rigid however for longer fibres this may not be the case and a model for flexible fibres should be included. It is also interesting to note that 82% of total fibres are aligned within $\pm 5^\circ$.

Figure 6: Fibre alignment for case with 3 mm, 4.5 mm, and 6 mm fibres together with a plate spacing of 0.3 mm.

4.5 Effect of changing contact angle

Another fibre parameter that could be changed is the type of fibre used. Whereas the previous results used carbon fibres it is possible to use many different types such as cellulose fibres. Fibres of different materials will have different contact angles. Therefore, the effect of different fibre contact angles was investigated. The contact angles used were 20°, 60°, and 80° with 3 mm fibres and a plate spacing of 0.3mm. All other simulation parameters were the same as listed in Table 1. The result for the final fibre alignment for the three different contact angles is shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen that there is not much difference in alignment between 20° and 60° but increasing the contact angle to 80° decreases the alignment. The amount of fibres oriented within $\pm 3^\circ$ was 80% for a contact angle of 20° and 76% for a contact angle of 60° but dropped to 55% for a contact angle of 80°. This is could be caused by the higher contact angle resulting in less wetting of the fibre and therefore more movement on the belt.

Figure 7: Fibre alignment for different fibre contact angles and a plate spacing of 0.3 mm: 20° (top), 60° (middle), and 80° (bottom).

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a smoothed particle hydrodynamics based computational model for the manufacture of highly aligned discontinuous fibre composite tapes. The model accounts for all fluid-fibre interactions as well as other features of the HiPerDiF alignment head such as the peristaltic pump, pressure-driven fluid drainage and conveyer belt. The model has been validated against experiments by

changing the plate spacing and assessing the overall fibre alignment. It was shown that the model is able to successfully capture the affect of varying the plate spacing on the fibre alignment. Initial investigations into the effect of using different lengths and types of fibres has also been presented. Future work will focus on investigating how other parameters affect the fibre alignment in order to assist in developing a upscaled design capable of producing higher quantities of high-quality material.

Plate spacing (mm)	Fibre length (mm)	Contact angle of fibres (degrees)	Alignment (%)
0.3	3.0	60	76
0.5	3.0	60	44
1.0	3.0	60	27
0.3	3.0,4.5,6.0	60	66
0.3	3.0	20	80
0.3	3.0	80	55

Table 2: Summary of fibre alignment within $\pm 3^\circ$ for all simulations

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) “High Performance Discontinuous Fibre Composites - A sustainable route to the next generation of composites” [EP/P027393/] grant.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Longana, N. Ong, H. Yu, and K. Potter. “Multiple closed loop recycling of carbon fibre composites with the HiPerDiF (high performance discontinuous fibre) method”. *Composite Structures*, Vol. 153, pp 271–277, 2016.
- [2] M. Such, C. Ward, and K. Potter, “Aligned discontinuous fibre composites: A short history,” *Journal of Multifunctional Composites*, Vol. 3, 2014.
- [3] H. Yu, M. Longana, M. Jalalvand, M. Wisnom, and K. Potter. “Hierarchical pseudo-ductile hybrid composites combining continuous and highly-aligned discontinuous fibres”. *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 105, pp 40–56, 2018.
- [4] S. Kulasegaram, B. Karihaloo, and A. Ghanbari, “Modelling the flow of self-compacting concrete,” *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics*, Vol. 35, pp. 713–723, 2011.
- [5] R. Deeb, S. Kulasegaram, and B. Karihaloo, “3d modelling of the flow of self-compacting concrete with or without steel fibres. part i: slump flow test,” *Computational Particle Mechanics*, Vol. 1, pp. 373–389, 2014.
- [6] P. Cleary, J. Ha, M. Prakash, and T. Nguyen, “3d sph flow predictions and validation for high pressure die casting of automotive components,” *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, Vol. 30, pp. 1406–1427, 2006.
- [7] P. Cleary and J. Ha, “Three-dimensional smoothed particle hydrodynamics simulation of high pressure die casting of light metal components,” *Journal of Light Metals*, Vol. 2, pp. 169–183, 2009.
- [8] P. Cleary, J. Ha, M. Prakash, and T. Nguyen, “Short shots and industrial case studies: Understanding fluid flow and solidification in high pressure die casting,” *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, Vol. 34, pp. 2018–2033, 2010.
- [9] P. Cleary, G. Savage, J. Ha, and M. Prakash, “Flow analysis and validation of numerical modelling for a thin walled high pressure die casting using sph,” *Computational Particle Mechanics*, Vol. 1, pp. 229– 243, 2014.
- [10] D. Su, R. Ma, and L. Zhu, “Numerical study of liquid composite molding using a smoothed particle hydrodynamics method,” *Special Topics & Reviews in Porous Media - An International Journal*, Vol. 2, pp. 205–216, 2011.
- [11] X. Xu, J. Ouyang, B. Yang, and Z. Liu, “Sph simulations of three dimensional non-newtonian free surface flows,” *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanical Engineering*, Vol. 256, pp. 101–116, 2013.
- [12] L. He, G. Lu, D. Chen, W. Li, and C. Lu, “Three-dimensional smoothed particle hydrodynamics simulation for injection molding of short fiber-reinforced polymer composites,” *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering*, Vol. 25, no. 055007, 2017.

- [13] D. Yang, K. Wu, L. Wan, and Y. Sheng, "A particle element approach for modelling the 3d printing process of fibre reinforced polymer composites," *Journal of Manufacturing and Materials Processing*, Vol. 1, no. 10, 2017.
- [14] T. Tofighi, M. Ozbulut, A. Rahmat, J. Feng, and M. Yildiz, "An incompressible smoothed particle hydrodynamics method for the motion of rigid bodies in fluids," *Journal of Computational Physics*, Vol. 297, pp. 207–220, 2015.
- [15] M. Hashemi, R. Fatehi, and M. Manzari, "A modified sph method for simulating motion of rigid bodies in newtonian fluid flows," *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics*, Vol. 47, pp. 626–638, 2012.
- [16] A. Aly and M. Asai, "Large scale simulation of fluid-structure interaction using an incompressible smoothed particle hydrodynamics," in 11th World Congress on Computational Mechanics, E. Oate, J. Oliver, and A. Huerta, Eds., Vol. 11. *International Association for Computational Mechanics*, 2014.
- [17] K. Skoptsov, V. Sheshenin, V. Galatenko, A. Malakho, N. Shornikova, V. Avdeev, and V. Sadovnichy, "Particle simulation for predicting effective properties of short fiber reinforced composites," *International Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 8, no. 1650016, 2016.
- [18] R. Deeb, S. Kulasegaram, and B. Karihaloo, "3d modelling of the flow of self-compacting concrete with or without steel fibres. part ii: L-box test and the assessment of fibre reorientation during the flow." *Computational Particle Mechanics*, Vol. 1, pp. 391–408, 2014.
- [19] M. Khodadadi Yazdi, A. Ramazani S.A., A. Kamyabi, and H. Hosseini Amoli, "Simulation of flow of short fiber suspensions through a planar contraction," *Transactions C: Chemistry and Chemical Engineering*, Vol. 19, pp. 579–584, 2012.
- [20] A. Oumer, N. Hamidi, and I. Mat Sahat, "Numerical prediction of flow induced fibers orientation in injection molded polymer composites," in *IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, Vol. 100. IOP Publishing Ltd, 2015.
- [21] J. Hamalainen, T. Hamalainen, T. Leppanen, H. Niskanen, and J. Sorvari, "Mathematics in paper - from fiber suspension fluid dynamic to solid state paper mechanics," *Journal of Mathematics in Industry*, Vol. 4, no. 14, 2014.
- [22] H. Yu, K. Potter, and M. Wisnom, "A novel manufacturing method for aligned discontinuous fibre composites (high performance-discontinuous fibre method)," *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 65, pp. 175–185, 2014.
- [23] J. Morris, P. Fox, and Y. Zhu. "Modeling low Reynolds number incompressible flow using SPH". *Journal of Computational Physics*, Vol. 136, pp 214–226, 1997.
- [24] A. Tartakovsky and P. Meakin. "Modeling of surface tension and contact angles with smoothed particle hydrodynamics". *Physical Review E: Statistical, Nonlinear, and Soft Matter Physics*, Vol. 72, no. 026301, pp 1-9, 2005.
- [25] A. Crespo, M. Gomez-Gestaira, and R. Dalrymple. "Boundary conditions generated by dynamic particles in SPH methods". *Computers, Materials & Continua*, Vol. 5, no. 3, pp 173–184, 2007.
- [26] J. Hall, T. Rendall, C. Allen, and H. Peel, "A multi-physics computational model of fuel sloshing effects on aeroelastic behaviour," *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, Vol. 56, pp. 11–32, 2015.
- [27] A. Tartakovsky and A. Panchenko. "Pairwise force smoothed particle hydrodynamics model for multiphase flow: surface tension and contact line dynamics". *Journal of Computational Physics*, Vol. 305, pp. 1119-1146, 2016.
- [28] S. Huntley, T. Rendall, M. Longana, T. Pozegic, K. Potter and I. Hamerton. "Recycling composite materials using a water-jet tape deposition method". *Proceedings of the 13th International SPHERIC workshop*, Galway, Ireland, Vol. 13, pp 357-364, 2018